

“A Comparative Study of Educational Contribution of School Management Committees in Tribal and Non-Tribal Areas”.

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Abstract

For the purpose of section 21 of the ‘Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009’, all primary schools (excluding unaided schools) were directed to establish School Management Committees before 30th September, 2010. Accordingly, School Management Committees have been established in all primary schools. In the present research, the researcher has conducted a comparative study of the educational contribution of School Management Committees in Zilla Parishad primary schools in tribal and non-tribal areas. For this, descriptive survey method has been adopted. There are 14 talukas in Ahilyanagar district, out of which 4 talukas were selected by lottery method. School Management Committee Chairpersons 100, School Management Committee Secretaries 100 and School Inspectors 25 each from tribal and non tribal areas of the Zilla Parishad primary Schools were selected by random sampling method. Information was collected from the respondents through questionnaires, opinionnaires and checklists. Statistical analysis of the obtained data was done by using the statistical technique of percentage.

Key words:

Tribal area, non-tribal area, School Management Committee, educational contribution.

Introduction:

Various commissions and committees related to education in India have made recommendations regarding community participation in education. The **Kothari Commission** (1964-1966) recommended ‘local community participation in schools and decentralization of school management’ for the improvement of education. The **Education Policy 1968** recommended that ‘schools should be brought closer to the community, and community participation is essential for achieving the objective of free and compulsory education for all children between the age group of 6 to 14 years’. The **Education Policy, 1986** recommended that ‘local community participation is essential for ensuring enrolment, attendance and quality education’.

According to **Article 45 of the Indian Constitution**, it was the responsibility of the government to provide free and compulsory primary education to children between the age group of 6 to 14 years within a period of ten years after independence. According to the **73rd and 74th constitutional amendments** of the Indian Constitution, it will be possible to monitor the objectives of **universalization of education**, out-of-school student survey, maintenance and

repair of school buildings, and attendance of teachers in schools. For this, emphasis was given to the active participation of the **Village Education Committees**.

Need for Research:

School Management Committee has to do the school monitoring, prepare a school development plan, monitor utilisation of funds received by government and other resources and school MDM scheme. Therefore, the present research work will clarify the current status of the school in terms of school monitoring, school development plan preparation, follow-up of teachers' duties and solving teachers' problems, reducing the burden of non-academic work on teachers, 100% attendance and 100% enrollment, education of children with special needs, review of children's academic progress, monitoring of school mid-day meal scheme, creation, development and maintenance of school physical facilities.

Once the current status of the school management committee is clear, if necessary, it is possible to focus on some important issues. Measures can be taken to improve the functioning of school management committees. Also, what is the exact current status of school management committees in tribal areas? Does the educational contribution of school management committees in tribal and non-tribal areas make a difference in the work? If there is a difference, why? The researcher feels it is necessary to explore all these issues.

Importance of the Research:

As per the '**Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009**' directions were given to set up School Management Committees for all management primary schools except unaided schools for school management, planning and implementation. Accordingly, School Management Committees have been set up in all schools before 30 September 2010. According to RTE Act, 2009 responsibilities of School Management Committee are planning, implementation and supervision. Comparing the functioning of school management committees in tribal and non-tribal areas will help to understand the similarities and differences in the work of school management committees. Therefore, if there are any differences, the reasons can be found. Based on the findings, some recommendations can be made to improve the work of school management committees. A large amount of research has been done in India regarding school management committees, but since no research work has been done on the subject of 'Comparative study of educational contribution of school management committees in Zilla Parishad schools in tribal and non-tribal areas' in Maharashtra and especially in Ahilyanagar district, researcher has undertaken the research work.

Review of related literature:

For the present research, the researcher has reviewed the previous research related to the research topic:

Rot (2014), 'Work of School Management Committees in Rural Areas: A Study'. According to School Management Committees, 100% enrolment and 100% attendance are contributed by school management committees. Similarly, regular attendance of teachers and school supervision are done. But it is seen that the teacher-student ratio is not being worked on.

Kumar (2016), 'Role of School Management Committees in Mann Government Secondary Schools in Kullu District, Himachal Pradesh: A Study', according to which the School Management Committees have been established as per RTE norms and majority of the School Management Committee members are aware of the functions and responsibilities of the School

Management Committee. The School Management Committee plays a significant role in preparing the school development plan. This helps in developing the basic facilities in the school.

Rajbhongshi (2020), ‘Study on the role of School Management Committee in School Supervision and Monitoring in Primary Schools in Sibsagar District, Assam’. According to the study School Management Committee members are not aware of the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009 and therefore cannot make a significant contribution to the School Management Committee. The School Management Committee members and the Chairpersons need training.

Objectives of the study:

- 1) To conduct a comparative study of the current status of School Management Committees in tribal and non-tribal areas
- 2) To conduct a comparative study of the educational contribution of School Management Committees in tribal and non-tribal areas.
- 3) To study the problems faced by School Management Committees in tribal and non-tribal areas.
- 4) To compare the current status, contribution and problems of School Management Committees in tribal and non-tribal areas.
- 5) To suggest measures to make the contribution of School Management Committees in tribal and non-tribal areas effective.

Research Questions:

- 1) What is the current status of School Management Committees in primary schools in tribal areas?
- 2) What is the current status of School Management Committees in primary schools in non-tribal areas?
- 3) In which aspects are there similarities and differences in the current status of School Management Committees in tribal and non-tribal areas?
- 4) Who contributes the most in which aspects to the School Management Committees in primary schools in tribal areas?
- 5) Who contributes the most in which aspects to the School Management Committees in non-tribal areas?

Delimitations of the study:

There were certain delimitation of the present study.

1. The study was delimited to the comparison of contribution by School Management Committees.
2. The present study was also delimited to the comparison of contribution by School Management Committees in zillaparishd primary schools from tribal and non tribal areas.
3. The present study was also delimited to to the comparison of contribution by School Management Committees in zillaparishd primary schools from tribal and non tribal areas of Ahilyanagar district.

Method of the study:

The present research has studied the current situation and the researcher has chosen the **descriptive survey method** to know the facts and realities of the present time.

Population and Sample:

1) Population:

The main objective of the study is to compare the educational contribution of school management committees of tribal and non tribal areas in Ahilyanagar district. There are 14 educational blocks in Ahilyanagar district. All zilla parishad schools, all school management committees, all SMC chairpersons, all SMC secretaries and all school observers were included in the population of the study.

2) Sample:

There are 14 education blocks in Ahilyanagar district, out of which 4 blocks were selected by **lottery method**. School Management Committee Chairpersons 100, School Management Committee Secretaries 100 and School Observers 25 each from tribal and non tribal areas of the Zilla Parishad primary Schools were selected by **random sampling method**.

Sr.No	Area	SMC chairman	%	SMC secretary	%	School observer	%
1.	Tribal	100	50%	100	50%	25	67%
2.	Non tribal	100	5%	100	5%	25	18%
Total		200	-	200		50	-

Research Methodology

Research tools:

For the purpose of the present research, the researcher has used the following three tools for data collection:

- A) Questionnaire (School Management Committee Chairman)
- B) Opinionnaire (School Management Committee Secretary)
- C) Checklist (School Observer)

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

The researcher used different statistical techniques to classify and interpret the information obtained through data collection tools.

Tabulation:

Tables were used to classify the questions and responses received in the research tools.

Classification:

The researcher used classification technique to classify the collected data for the purpose of analysis and interpretation.

Graph:

The researcher used graphs at some places to analyze and interpret the collected data. Due to this, there was more clarity in the analysis and interpretation. It became easier to draw conclusions.

Conclusion:

- 1) School Management Committee has been established in almost all the schools in tribal and non-tribal areas as per RTE criteria.
- 2) Almost all the school management committee members in tribal and non-tribal areas have been elected from the parent meeting.
- 3) Almost all school management members in tribal and non-tribal areas are represented as per RTE norms.
- 4) Most school management committee meetings in non-tribal areas have member attendance as per norms.
- 5) Most school management committee members in non-tribal areas are aware about the management committee powers and functions.
- 6) Most school management committee members in tribal areas are reluctant to attend meetings.
- 7) Most school management committee meetings in tribal areas have very low attendance of women members.
- 8) Most school management committee members in tribal areas need to be sensitized.
- 9) Most school management committees in tribal areas are reluctant to write minutes of meetings.
- 10) School management committees are reconstituted every two years in almost all schools in tribal and non-tribal areas.
- 11) Most school management committee members in tribal and non-tribal areas have been sensitized about the school management committee powers and responsibilities.
- 12) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas take action against teachers' misconduct and irregularities.
- 13) Most school management committee members in non-tribal areas are involved in various school activities.
- 14) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas provide study facilities to students.
- 15) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas review the preparation of various competitive exams conducted by the government.
- 16) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas focus on developing physical facilities as per the school development plan.

- 17) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas monitor school repairs and school construction.
- 18) Almost all school management committees in tribal and non-tribal areas follow up to provide safe drinking water.
- 19) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas try to provide playgrounds and sports equipment.
- 20) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas try to provide library books, magazines and newspapers in the school.
- 21) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas prepare annual income and expenditure records of the school.
- 22) Almost all school management committees in tribal and non-tribal areas make income and expenditure records available to all upon request.
- 23) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas monitor teacher attendance.
- 24) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas resolve teacher problems.
- 25) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas contribute to the school for student registration and student attendance.
- 26) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas review curriculum completion.
- 27) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas only check the records kept by the teachers.
- 28) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas prepare a school development plan by consensus keeping in mind the needs of the school.
- 29) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas follow up more for the development of physical facilities.
- 30) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas contribute to raising public participation for the school.
- 31) School management committee members in tribal areas have low participation in school activities.
- 32) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas control the use of funds received from the government.
- 33) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas keep school nutrition records up to date.
- 34) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas check the progress records kept by teachers.
- 35) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas strive for 100% enrolment and 100% attendance.
- 36) Most school management committees in Bidar tribal areas strive to keep out-of-school students in the flow of education.
- 37) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas strive to provide essential learning facilities to students.
- 38) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas work on developing physical facilities as per the school development plan.
- 39) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas monitor school repairs and school construction.
- 40) Most school management committees in non-tribal areas monitor the utilization of funds received from the government or other sources.
- 41) Most school management committees in tribal areas face problems in developing physical facilities due to lack of funds.
- 42) Most school management committees in tribal areas face problems due to non-availability of school nutrition grants and food grains.
- 43) Most school management committees in tribal areas face problems due to non-availability of funds for developing physical facilities.
- 44) Most school management committees in tribal areas do not receive school nutrition grants and food grains.
- 45) School management committees face problems due to non-availability of school nutrition grants and food grains.

Recommendations

For SMC.Chairpersons:

- 1) The School Management Committee Chairperson should study the RTE Act, 2009.
- 2) School Management Committee members from tribal areas should be encouraged to attend regularly.
- 3) The Secretary of the School Management Committee should complete the minutes of the School Management Committee meeting with the signature of the Chairman in a timely manner.
- 4) The School Management Committee Secretary should brief the School Management Committee Chairman and members regarding the functions and responsibilities of the School Management Committee.
- 5) School Management committee meetings should be organised according to the women members timing and members going for employment.
- 6) School Management Committee chairperson should ensure that the minutes of the School Management Committees are to be completed in a timely manner.
- 7) The School Management Committee chairperson should get done the school development plan according to the school priorities.

For SMC secretaries:

- 1) The SMC secretary should give prior notice of the SMC meeting to all members.
- 2) The SMC secretary should give information about the functions and responsibility of SMC to the members and chairperson.

For school bservers:

- 1) School observer should take the review of School Management Committee meetings regularly.
- 2) School observer should regularly attend SMC meetings and address the SMC members and chairpersons.

For government:

- 1) Government should organise the training of SMC members and chairpersons.
- 2) Government should arrange the SMC member's visits to the schools where SMCs are functioning in wel manner.

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